

An OBE curriculum design for a Manufacturing Engineering program, from Thai traditional to outcome based education

Wanida Rattanamanee¹, Kunlapat Thongkaew¹, Supapan Chaiprapat¹, Suriya Jirasatitsin¹, Chukree Daesa¹ and Pichet Trakarnchaisiri¹

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand

Email: wanida.r@psu.ac.th, tkunlapat@eng.psu.ac.th, supapan.s@psu.ac.th, suriya.j@psu.ac.th, chukree.d@psu.ac.th, pichet.t@psu.ac.th

Abstract

Outcome based education (OBE) has been gaining popularity as an objective in a modern curriculum design. The outcomes imposed reveal what students are expected to accomplish by the end of the program of study. This paper aims to present a transformation of Thai traditional curriculum, a manufacturing engineering program, to be an OBE curriculum. The CDIO framework and requirements of the ABET accreditation system were applied in the design process. Work Integrated Learning approach was employed to provide opportunities for students to gain practical experiences from workplace for at least 1 year. Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs) were formulated out of a survey conducted with the program stakeholders, resulting in 10 PLOs. Knowledge, attitude and skills essential in achieving the PLOs were identified and translated into courses totalled up to 138 credits. All courses will be planned and operated systematically from content design through assessment. Active learning techniques are prioritized in conducting classes to promote student engagement with class activities. More involvement of stakeholders narrows down the gap previously existed between their needs and what the institution offered. With international accreditation in addition, graduates from this new curriculum now are given professional opportunities worldwide.

Keywords: OBE; CDIO; ABET; Curriculum design

1 Introduction

Over the last decade, many components of manufacturing systems have been rapidly changed due to the fourth industrial revolution. Advancement technologies, such as Internet of things, Cloud manufacturing and rapid prototyping empower customers to demand better responsiveness. As such, an emerging smart manufacturing system is designed to respond in real time to meet the ever-changing demands and conditions in the factory. Employees are also expected to be equipped with advanced skills, such as complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, judgment and decision making, etc. (WEF, 2016). Therefore, the graduated students who will be a manufacturing engineer should have their knowledge and competences to be ready for this new environment. However, the development of the students' competences will be not successful if the learning is improperly designed. Based on reviewing literature, most existing engineering curriculums have been designed principally based on a traditional curriculum model that stakeholder needs were not significantly considered to design a curriculum (Dym et al. 2005). In addition, teaching and learning subjects were developed depending on lecturers' knowledge or what they would like to teach. For example, a traditional manufacturing engineering curriculum in Thailand (PSU, 2016), four years study with approximately 146 academic credits was designed, and more than three quarters of developed subjects are based on theory, not practical subjects. With the study plan, the sequences of teaching subjects was not well organized in the connection between fundamental and advanced knowledge, leading to lack of continuous learning. At the fourth year students have their internships or do their cooperative education projects with industries in a short time period about one semester. This might not encourage students to gain deep experience.

Several selected papers related to curriculum development were reviewed in this research work (Mesquita et al. 2015; Mesquita et al. 2018; Lima et al. 2017). There were three challenges faced by university curriculum development in higher education. The first one was the relationship between teacher planning and pedagogical action, content selection processes and teaching strategies. The second one was the development

of the students' competences. The last challenge was the emphasis on assessment as one of the key enhancers of curriculum innovation (Mesquita et al. 2018). In order to success these challenge, there are several techniques to develop curricula such as, Project-Based Learning (PBL) (Lima et al. 2017) and Outcome-Based Education (OBE) (Youhasan et al., 2019). The PBL had been used to develop the competency of students while working in industries by Lima et al. (2017) for Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) curriculum. The framework of competences was developed through a process of analysis using a combination of methods and sources for data collection. There were four main steps including; characterization of knowledge areas, definition of competences, survey and application of the framework at the curriculum. The OBE also has vital in curriculum development. Youhasan et al. (2019) employed this principle for MBBS program (medical graduation in Eastern University, Sri Lanka. They found that the OBE curriculum had specific features and met the current trends and needs of medical education locally as well as internationally.

According the reviewing literature, therefore, this paper aim to developed a manufacturing engineer curriculum from traditional to outcome-based education (OBE) in order to produce graduated students having knowledge and skills to solve the real problems, and having good relationship among people in the systems. The OBE has been proved to an effective education principle to design curriculums as it is focused learning outcomes or graduated students competencies that are the most importance for designing curriculums (Ayyappan et al. 2019). CDIO framework ABET accreditation system were also applied in the design process. Finally, Work Integrated Learning (WIL) approach was employed to provide opportunities for students to gain practical experiences from industries. With the developed curriculum techniques, students will be taught systematically following to the program learning outcomes that enhance the student to have their better competences and stronger experience rather than the traditional curriculum concept.

2 Conceptual Background

2.1 OBE approach

OBE methods have been adopted in education systems around the world, at multiple levels (Eldeeb and NishaShatakumari, 2013). OBE can primarily be distinguished from traditional education method by the way it incorporates three elements: theory of education, a systematic structure for education, and a specific approach to instructional practice (Killen, 2007). OBE approach aims to obtain a well-designed educational system that offers a clear outcomes for all students to be able to accomplish by the end of their learning experience (Ayyappan et al. 2019). According to this purpose, students will understand what is expected of them and teachers will also know what they need to teach. The implementation of OBE requires consistency across desired outcomes of education, teaching and learning activities, and assessment methods and practices (Spady, 1994). The desired outcomes should be based on skills, such as life, professional and vocational, intellectual, interpersonal and personal, that students will perform in the real world. The operating principle of program design based on OBE is a downward direction from the culminating outcomes of program level to the course outcomes that are measured by specific learning tasks. In addition, the outcomes of course and program levels should be fundamentally linked to the culminating outcomes of education. Hence, in this study, OBE approach emphasizes on the utilization of CDIO framework, ABET accreditation system and work Integrated Learning approach in order to achieve OBE curriculum design for a Manufacturing Engineering program. The concepts of CDIO framework, ABET accreditation system and work Integrated Learning approach are discussed in the following topics.

2.2 CDIO framework

CDIO framework is an innovative educational framework for producing the 21th engineers that have been adopted in many universities (Pee and Leong, 2006; Lee et al., 2015). The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving — Designing — Implementing — Operating (CDIO) real-world systems and products (Crawley, 2001). CDIO's emphasis on active learning

encourages students to take more active roles in their own learning. The development of program is considered based on the mapping of four expectations; technical, personal, inter-personal and CDIO. A mature individual interested in technical attempts dominates a set of personal and professional skills. In order to develop complex value-added engineering systems, students must have mastered the fundamentals of the appropriate technical knowledge and reasoning. On the other hand, the interpersonal skills of teamwork and communications develop students for working in a modern team-based environment. Finally, in order to actually be able to create and operate products and systems, a student must understand something of conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating systems (Crawley, 2001). In order to evaluate the developed program, CDIO also conducts 12 standards (Lee et al., 2015); CDIO as the context, CDIO syllabus outcomes, integrated curriculum, introduction to engineering, design build experiences, CDIO workspaces, integrated learning experiences, active learning, enhancement of staff CDIO skills, enhancement of staff teaching skills, CDIO skills assessment and CDIO program evaluation. The standards are divided into six standard groups, that is standards for curriculum, workspace/labs, teaching and learning methods, enhance of faculty competence, and assessment methods. Some educational criteria and approaches, such as ABET accreditation, STEEP analysis and knowledge taxonomies are usually applied with CDIO framework to develop engineering curriculums (Crawley, 2011). STEEP analysis is a popular framework applied to explore future trends and their implications through five categories: social & demographic, technology, economic, environment & nature, political & legal (Lee et al., 2018)

2.3 ABET accreditation system

ABET accreditation provides assurance that a university program meets the international quality standards of the profession in area of engineering, which worldwide universities has been applied (Bachnak et al., 2019). This is because students can graduate with a unique array of personal, interpersonal, and system-building experiences that allows them to stand out in real engineering teams, and produce new products and systems. According ABET accreditation system; all approved programs must achieve all of the eight criteria for Baccalaureate Level Programs. The criteria include student criterion, program educational objectives criterion, student outcomes criterion, continuous improvement criterion, curriculum criterion, faculty criterion, facilities criterion and institutional support criterion (ABET, 2017). For the fifth criterion of curriculum, the curriculum requirements specify subject areas appropriate to engineering. In addition, the program curriculum must devote adequate attention and time to each component, consistent with the outcomes and objectives of the program and institution. The professional component must include a combination of college level mathematics and basic sciences appropriate to the discipline, engineering topics both in engineering sciences and engineering design appropriate to the student's field of study. Finally, a general education component that enhances the technical content of the curriculum related with the program and institution objectives has to take into account. With the application of ABET accreditation for manufacturing engineering programs (ABET, 2017), the program should prepare graduates to have proficiency in five main areas; materials and manufacturing processes; process, assembly and product engineering; manufacturing competitiveness; manufacturing systems design and manufacturing laboratory or facility experience. As the result of this, students are prepared for manufacturing engineering practice to meet engineering standards and multiple realistic constraints.

2.4 Work Integrated Learning approach

Work Integrated Learning (WIL) is the term given to an activity or program that integrates academic learning with its application in the workplace. The practice may be real or simulated and can occur in the workplace, at university, online, face-to-face or any combination of these. WIL involves developing students' work readiness skills to industry standards and enhancing employability. Many universities have been included WIL in engineering programs (Edwards et al. 2015; Monash University, 2018). With WIL concept, students can contribute vibrant and diverse perspectives, knowledge, analytical and research skills. They can also explore solutions to real-world problems, exercise critical thinking and professional judgement and show technical skill in designing, conducting and reporting on a research project. These lead students to be flexible, talented, capable, enthusiastic, experienced for working. However, the achievement of WIL application is largely relying

on individual students to find placements, which a more integrated approach is required to provide good quality work experience for university students (AWPA, 2014). Nevertheless, WIL can provide a potential source of inspiration in finding workplace models that are applicable beyond engineering and it might create pathways into sustainable employment for graduates (Stiwne and Jungert, 2010).

3 The Existing Curriculum

Usually for a traditional manufacturing engineering curriculum, the development of program learning outcomes (PLOs) has not systematically considered stakeholder expectations (Zou et al., 2012). In addition, the PLOs were not significantly related to course learning outcomes. There was also no assessment how competencies of students to the PLOs. Lecturers designed their own course objectives and focus on specifically course content. There was also no consideration the relationship among courses, and the course assessment methods were not clarified as such a rubric assessment that students can be scored equally (Chong and Romkey, 2012). In addition, students took courses with quite far different areas, leading to lose the concentration for the sequence subjects. Due to the limited time, students cannot also comprehend appropriately the concepts and develop their skills of a disciplinary area. According to these, students might clearly understand and gain knowledge and skills from the courses to achieve the PLOs. Figure 1 shows the current Manufacturing Engineering curriculum, Prince of Songkla University (PSU, 2016).

Figure 1 The current teaching and learning plan of Manufacturing Engineering program (PSU, 2016).

From the curriculum, there are 146 credits for four years study, where each semesters is dedicated on average of 21 credits. In the first year, most basic science knowledge for engineer is planned to study and most courses are in the disciplinary area. Most specific knowledge for engineer is included in study plan in the second year, while most specific knowledge for manufacturing engineer is contained in the third year. After third year, there are two study options, doing general project or doing cooperative project with industries. Practical training is registered for project option during the third year summer, another cooperative course is taken during the first semester for the fourth year. In this year, most courses are selective subjects, depending on students' interest subjects to fulfill their own knowledge. It can be seen that about 19 credits are determined for general area to improve general knowledge and skills, whereas approximately 23 credits are defined for interdisciplinary area to integrate specific knowledge and the other engineering field such as computer for engineering, free elective courses, etc. The left credits were specific knowledge for manufacturing engineering. Apart from that, the courses are in disciplinary area, in which specific knowledge subjects are determined in many groups, such as manufacturing process, manufacturing management and computer aided manufacturing. However, the

sequence of teaching and learning courses is not properly design. The connection among courses for each knowledge group is also not considered seriously. This results in lack of understating in the relationship between courses and the concentration of the specific group subjects.

4 Implementation of OBE approach

4.1 Manufacturing Engineering program

With OBE proposed approach, the Manufacturing Engineering program was designed following the CDIO framework, ABET accreditation system and Work Integrated Learning approach. First of all, stakeholders having power to the program were listed and grouped into levels of their power to the program and the impact from the program to them, as shown in Table 1. The stakeholders in the group of high power and high impact are the first priority to consider their needs, following by high power and low impact, low power and high impact, and low power and low impact, respectively. In addition, more involvement of stakeholders able to narrows down the gap previously existed between their needs and what the institution offered will be considered. Furthermore, STEEP analysis was applied to analyse the stakeholders' needs in terms of social, technological, economical, environmental, and political to design the curriculum PLOs. With STTEP analysis, the stakeholders' needs were summarized in each areas as for economical area, the knowledge and technologies for manufacturing sectors should be developed by focusing on innovation for basic and new industries in Thailand, support of researches for AI and collaborative technologies and preparation of human ability and infrastructures. For social area, the support of aging society, the reduction of labor force and migration from rural to urban areas are required. For technological area, world trend technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, machine learning, internet of thing (IOT) and smart city to transform to Industrial 4.0 should be focused. For environmental area, green energy, alternative energy, recycled materials and climate change/low carbon society are major concerns. The regulations relating to environment and terrorism are the issues for political area. Finally, the developed PLOs was evaluated by ABET accreditation system to meet an international education standard. With the international accreditation, graduates from this new developed curriculum are now given professional opportunities worldwide. The program learning outcomes (PLOs) were formulated out of a survey conducted by the program stakeholders, resulting in 10 PLOs for Manufacturing Engineering program, as shown in Table 2. The relationship between the PLOs and the ABET student's outcomes is presented in Table 3, while the relationship between the stakeholders' needs and the PLOs is shown in Table 4.

Table 1. Classification of power of stakeholders and impact on stakeholders

Power of stakeholders	Impact on stakeholders	
	High	Low
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher Education Commission - Industries - Thailand Council of Engineers - Prince of Songkla University - Engineering faculty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manufacturing engineering alumni - Industrial engineering department - Lectures
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General public

It can be seen from Table 2 that the PLOs were defined into generic and specific skills with a balance proportion, where PLOs 1-5 are specific skill and PLOs 6-10 are generic skill. The PLOs of specific skills result students' competence of knowledge, while the PLOs of generic skills contribute the attitude and skill competencies. PLO4 focuses on the student's capability of digital technology which is the advanced skill of 21st century education. PLO5 is the ultimate objective of the program. Innovator is the main attribute of the program to achieve the Thailand 4.0 policy. PLO7 is the key student's attribute of Prince of Songkla University as the students demonstrate social contributions. Besides, 11 attitudes and skills are also specified for the program including; creative thinking (1st – 2nd year), implement thinking (2nd – 3rd year), innovative thinking (3rd – 4th year), system thinking (4th year), self directed (1st – 2nd year), intrinsic motivation (3rd – 4th year), adaptable (1st – 4th year), open minded (1st – 4th year), system integration (3rd – 4th year), teamwork collaboration (1st – 4th year) and digital fabrication (2nd – 4th year).

Table 2. Program learning outcomes of OBE Manufacturing Engineering curriculum

Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs)	Generic Skill	Specific Skill
PLO1: An ability to identify, formulate and solve complex engineering problems of Thailand, the southern region in particular, by applying principles of engineering, science, and mathematics		✓
PLO2: An ability to apply modern engineering principles to develop innovations in collaboration with other disciplines		✓
PLO3: An ability to develop and conduct appropriate experimentation, analyze and interpret data, and use engineering judgement to draw conclusion		✓
PLO4 An ability to exploit digital technologies to design, test, inspect, control and manage manufacturing systems		✓
PLO5 An ability to design manufacturing engineering innovations that can be commercialized or eligible for patenting		✓
PLO6 An ability to acquire new knowledge to empower lifelong self-development	✓	
PLO7 An ability to demonstrate empathy, social contribution and prioritization on benefit of mankind	✓	
PLO8 An ability to recognize ethical and professional responsibilities in manufacturing engineering situations	✓	
PLO9 An ability to communicate using different modes of delivery such as writing reports, oral presenting, and elaborating effectively and understandably for international audiences	✓	
PLO10 An ability to function effectively on a team whose members together provide leadership, create a collaborative and inclusive environment, establish goals, plan tasks, and meet objectives	✓	

Table 3. the relationship between the new PLOs and the ABET student's

ABET students' outcomes	PLOs									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. an ability to apply knowledge of mathematics, science and engineering	✓									
2. an ability to design and conduct experiments, as well as to analyse and interpret data		✓								
3. an ability to design a system, component, or process to meet desired needs within realistic constraints such as economic, environmental, social, political, ethical, health and safety, manufacturability, and sustainability									✓	
4. an ability to function on multidisciplinary teams								✓		
5. an ability to identify, formulate, and solve engineering problems										✓
6. an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility			✓							
7. an ability to communicate effectively						✓				

Table 4. The relationship between the stakeholders' needs and the new PLOs

Stakeholders	Needs	PLOs									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Higher Education Commission	Have knowledge and ability in creating innovation; Have 21 st century skills; Have a professional ethics of engineering	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Industries	Have knowledge about manufacturing process design; Have skills about lifelong learning. Have actually work and motivation; Able to work with people who have different ideas; Able to communicate by English; Able to do work improvement, targeting and planning, and computer programming	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓

semesters (Table 6), and all the courses were developed corresponding to different categories; general, interdisciplinary and disciplinary areas, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 6. Teaching and learning plan of OBE Manufacturing Engineering program

Year	Teaching and learning plan		
	Semester 1	Semester2	Summer
1	- General Education subjects (2 credits) - Fundamental Engineering (18 credits)	- General Education subjects (7 credits) - Fundamental Manufacturing Engineering (14 credits)	-
2	- General Education subjects (4 credits) - Fundamental Manufacturing Engineering + Industrial PrBL (17 credits)	- General Education subjects (6 credits) - Fundamental Manufacturing Engineering + Industrial PrBL (15 credits)	-
3	- General Education subjects (3 credits) - Specific Manufacturing Engineering + Thin Sandwich (18 credits)	- General Education subjects (7 credits) - Elective subjects (6 credits) - Specific Manufacturing Engineering + Thin Sandwich (7 credits)	Practicum WBL
4	<u>Plan A</u> - Thick Sandwich + Industrial PrBL (7 credits) <u>Plan B</u> - Cooperative Education (7 credits)	<u>Plan A</u> - Thick Sandwich + Industrial PrBL (7 credits) <u>Plan B</u> - Cooperative Education (7 credits)	

Note Industrial PrBL: Industrial Project-based Learning, Practicum WBL: Practicum Work-based Learning, Thin Sandwich: Study mostly in University and sometimes in industry, Thick Sandwich: Study half in University and half in industry

Figure 2. Teaching and learning courses of OBE Manufacturing Engineering Program

It can be noticed that general education and fundamental engineering subjects are determined in first year, whereas specific subjects of Manufacturing Engineering are defined in third year. This leads students to have fundamental knowledge before learning advanced subjects. The involvement with industries was applied from the second year by industrial project-based learning and work integrated learning (i.e. thin sandwich and thick sandwich activities). The final fourth year, students can select their preferred plan, where Plan A is thick Sandwich + Industrial PrBL and Plan B is Cooperative Education. The difference between these two plans is that students will study half in University and half in industry for Plan A, while students will have a role as employee in industries for Plan B. From this design, one year WIL are implement to encourage students gaining

more practical experience. From Figure 2, the sequence of teaching and learning courses and the relationship between courses were considered in order to strengthen students' knowledge background before start learning specific/advanced subjects. For example, in order to achieve in learning the specific course of Machine Design, students need to pass fundamental courses of Math for QC and CAE, and Basic Machines. Course modules are also developed to combine related courses into one module. This can eliminate the problem of teaching the same subtopics and students can get better understanding and gain deeper knowledge. For instance, the course module of Manufacturing Process was developed to replace the courses of Manufacturing Process I, II and Manufacturing Process Laboratory I, II. All courses are planned and operated systematically from content design through assessment. Active learning techniques are prioritized in conducting classes to promote student engagement with class activities.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents the OBE curriculum design for a Manufacturing Engineering program, from Thai traditional to outcome based education. CDIO framework, ABET accreditation system and WIL concept have also been employed to conduct the OBE Manufacturing Engineering curriculum. It is apparent that 10 PLOs were developed based on the expectations of stakeholders. STEEP analysis was also applied to consider in dimensions of social, technological, economical, environmental, and political. Knowledge, attitude and skills essential in achieving the PLOs were identified and translated into courses totalled up to 138 credits. All courses were classified in to general, interdisciplinary and disciplinary areas and operated systematically as the teaching-learning sequence and the relationship between courses were taken into account. Course modules were also designed to replace related courses. With the international ABET accreditation, the developed graduates from this developed curriculum now are given professional opportunities worldwide. WIL approach was employed to design teaching-learning plan, in which students have opportunities to gain practical experiences from industries from the 3th year study. However, the OBE manufacturing engineering curriculum has not employed for teaching students yet. This curriculum should be further analysed and developed with stakeholders' feedbacks, such as higher education commission, students and industries to achieve in expected learning outcomes of the curriculum and meet their needs.

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